

Abstract

Many diseases can be picked up in hospitals, for obvious reasons. Is cancer one of them? Here I argue that this can be the case.

Afraid of cancer? Maybe it would help to stay away from hospitals...

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It is well known that the best place to pick up a disease is a place with greatest concentration of diseases - a hospital. However, no one believes that visiting hospitals might increase one's chances of getting cancer or some other disease that's not supposed to be infectious. But what if it's true?

Consider this.

Bits of naked bacterial DNA, probably from broken-open bacterial cells may often get integrated into nuclear DNA of cells of your body but it has been found that this (horizontal gene transfer from bacteria to a human cell) happens 210 times more often in tumor cells than in healthy cells[1].

Bacterial DNA has been found, for example, in acute myeloid leukemia and stomach adenocarcinoma. But not just any bacterial DNA, it was the DNA of *Acinetobacter* bacteria and those of *Pseudomonas* genus, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Both are often picked up in hospitals. The latter is especially feared for its resistance to multiple antibiotics.

So what's the reason behind this correlation, and is there causation?

Well, the horizontal gene transfer can indeed disrupt the cell genome in a way that allows runaway cell replication - triggering cancer.

Now, a healthy human cell generally won't exchange DNA with living bacteria, however, there is a good possibility that naked DNA (from dead bacteria) may get integrated into cell DNA during cell DNA repair. When does cell DNA damage occur, requiring repair? Generally, during exposure to high frequency radiation, or toxins.

This is how smoking can cause cancer. A lot of toxins are inhaled with each smoke. This leads to cell damage, which leads to repair, which may lead to integration of foreign DNA - which may cause cancer.

Conventional explanation, however, is that toxins damage cell DNA and it is the damage of parts of that DNA that usually protect us against

cancer, which increases the chances of getting cancer. The DNA repair mechanism is affected so the damage in the cell builds up. While this can certainly affect the body negatively, especially with many cells affected, how likely is that this alone will result in [malignant] runaway cell replication? The horizontal gene transfer may be a more likely cause.

The more one smokes the greater are the chances for cell damage and thus for more foreign DNA integration.

Now, if you have damaged cells and at the same time you're taking antibiotics, you also have a lot of dead bacteria, and thus, a lot of naked DNA floating around. This then further increases the chances that foreign DNA will be picked up during cell DNA repair.

And obviously, it does matter what DNA is picked up (Acinetobacter and Pseudomonas could be more likely to contain DNA that triggers cancer). Some people can smoke as much as they want and they may never get cancer. Is it because they don't take antibiotics and don't visit hospitals?

It may be so.

But the hypothesis can be even more strengthened. Consider this.

Usually, it is much more likely for a bacteria to acquire cell DNA than the other way around.

For bacteria, horizontal gene transfer is a replacement for sexual recombination so they have strong affinity for it and they practice it relatively regularly.

Now let's say one has damaged cells (ie. due to smoking). That means one may have naked cell DNA floating around that might get picked up by bacteria. And what if that DNA comes from a tumor cell (let's say a cell damaged by radiation therapy or chemotherapy). Now the gene that causes runaway cell replication may be carried by the bacteria that picked up the DNA.

And let's say that bacteria is the infectious Acinetobacter, or any other easily transmittable bacteria. You go to a hospital and pick it up. Later, you smoke a cigarette, take some antibiotics and, *voila*, you get cancer.

Now, I cannot say how likely this is to happen (where are the studies?) but it is definitely a possible scenario.

UPDATE 2023.08.13

Here's some very interesting synchronicity.

At the same day I published this, a study was published in Science where

researchers actually engineered *Acinetobacter* to detect tumor DNA[2]. In the process, tumor DNA is integrated into the genome of the bacteria! So now we have a bacteria specialized to capture tumor DNA. What could go wrong? If what I hypothesize here had low chance of occurring before, these chances have now been greatly increased. And they probably will further increase by human action.

Note that, with this mechanism, cancer (and not just cancer!) becomes effectively an infectious disease.

I am not a big smoker but I do smoke sometimes. I don't visit hospitals, I don't take antibiotics. I'm hardly ever sick.

My father does not smoke, but he does inhale toxins occasionally one way or another. He visits hospitals, he takes antibiotics, he's on all kinds of pills and he had cancer (operated).

I'm not a believer in strong causality though. I would say that a trip to a hospital may be synchronized with getting cancer - not that the trip caused it. Correlation is there. But possibility for relative causation exists.

The origin of cancer may involve a simple Darwinian mutation of particular genes - whether in bacteria, archaea or an eukaryotic cell. However, vertical gene transfer (inheritance) is not the only way to get them. It may be that, particularly in cases where the risk of cancer is not a result of inheritance, the horizontal gene transfer by bacteria plays a significant role.

But even in cases where these genes could have been inherited, are we sure that they did and have had a role in cancer? In example, it may be that a child has picked up a bacteria carrying the gene from a mother which has been taking chemotherapy, and that is what made the child more susceptible to cancer - not inheritance (although both may have a role).

A person who has inherited genes that make it more prone to cancer is more likely to take chemo/radiation therapy and antibiotics, at some point. For this reason, and due to the fact that orthodox reasoning does not favor horizontal gene transfer, the prime suspect for increased susceptibility to cancer of descendants may have been inherited genes. While inheritance certainly may play a role (particularly lifestyle affecting epigenetics) - rather than causing cancer, it may simply make a person more susceptible to horizontal gene transfer, which then may lead to cancer.

References

- [1] The tangled tree: A radical new history of life (2018), D. Quammen, 268

- [2] Engineered bacteria detect tumor DNA (2023), R. M. Cooper et al, Science 381(6658), 682-686
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adf3974>